

Expression of APikL effector family members in the blast fungus varies during plant infection

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ABSTRACT

This Technical Note complements our paper on the molecular evolution of the heavy-metal associated (HMA) domain binding effector candidate APikL2 and other APikL family members in the blast fungus *Magnaporthe oryzae* [1]. We identified a six gene family of lineage-specific effector candidates with sequence similarity to the well-characterized effector AVR-Pik. APikL2 and other members of the AVR-Pik like (APikL) family display potentially adaptive mutations in two distinct HMA-binding interfaces that influence binding specificity, similarly to mutations observed in AVR-Pik. However, whereas the function of AVR-Pik during infection is well documented, the role of other APikL family members remains to be determined, mainly because no resistance genes are known that recognize these effectors. Here, we investigated publicly available RNA-sequencing (RNA-seq) datasets to gain insights into the expression profiles of the APikL family members AVR-Pik, APikL2 and APikL5 in the rice infecting isolate ina168 and field transcriptomics samples of the 2016 wheat blast outbreak in Bangladesh. This analysis showed that expression of APikL family members varies in the examined datasets. While AVR-Pik is expressed in the rice infecting isolate ina168 during early infection, no reads mapped to APikL2. Similarly, no read coverage was observed at the APikL2 or APikL5 loci in field samples of wheat blast from Bangladesh. From this, we conclude that expression profiles of APikL members vary. However, to this date we cannot rule out if the other members of the APikL family are expressed in certain conditions, tissues, or host-species.

BACKGROUND

AVR-Pik, an HMA-binding effector of rice infecting isolates of *M. oryzae*, acquired amino acid polymorphisms that define HMA-binding specificity [2,3]. These polymorphic residues locate to distinct, surface exposed interfaces that mediate interaction with host targets of the small HMA-domain containing protein family (sHMA) and the extraneous integrated HMA domain of the rice immune receptor Pik-1 [4–6]. We recently identified five sequence related effector candidates in several genetic lineages of *M. oryzae* and *M. grisea*, that, together with AVR-Pik, form a six gene effector family [1]. We observed that polymorphic residues in two distinct

HMA-binding interfaces of APikL2 define the interaction specificity to sHMA proteins. Host-associated allelic diversification across the entire APikL family suggested that potentially adaptive mutations accumulate at these interfaces and that individual APikL effectors associate with specific host-lineages [1]. However, to date the role of APikL family members during infection of diverse host species is unknown. Effector expression is tightly regulated and often restricted to specific time point during infection or specific host species [7,8]. While AVR-Pik is expressed during early infection stages on rice and barley [7], expression of other APikL members has not yet been determined. In this technical note we report our findings obtained by analysing two publicly available RNA sequencing datasets, including a laboratory infection time-course of the rice blast isolate Ina168 in the barley cultivar “Nigrate” and a field transcriptomics dataset from the 2016 wheat blast outbreak in Bangladesh [7,9,10].

RESULTS

AVR-Pik and APikL2 show varying expression in the isolate Ina168 during early infection of barley

To determine expression profiles of APikL family members, we took advantage of two publicly available RNA-seq datasets. These datasets include a laboratory infection time course experiment of the rice blast isolate Ina168 on the susceptible barley cultivar “Nigrate” and a field transcriptomics dataset acquired during the 2016 wheat blast outbreak in Bangladesh [7,9,10]. The ina168 dataset included conidia and several stages during the early infection process, ranging from 12 to 48 hours post inoculation (HPI). The exact stage of disease progression of the wheat blast sample is unknown as these samples were taken from naturally infected material in the field.

We first mapped the raw reads of all Ina168 time points (conidia, 12 hpi, 24 hpi, 36 hpi and 48 hpi) to the Ina168 genome assembly (DDBJ accession number: DRZ007458; [11]) using STAR [12]. We then identified loci of several known effector genes, including AVR-Pik, APikL2, AVR-Pizt, AVR-Pi9, Bas1, and Slp1 using TBLASTN [13] and visualized RNA-seq read coverage in Integrated Genomics Viewer (IGV v2.3.91). All analysed effector genes were expressed in planta from 24 to 48 hpi, except for APikL2 that was not expressed under these conditions (Fig 1). For AVR-Pi9 and Slp1 we also observed weak expression in the conidial stage, although coverage was increased during later infection stages.

Fig 1. Plot of Ina168 RNA-Seq read coverage in Integrative genomics viewer. Alignment of RNA-Seq data from different stages of *M. oryzae* isolate Ina168 infection on peeled epidermal cotyledon tissue of susceptible barley *Hordeum vulgare* cv. “Nigrata” mapped to a selection of known effector genes including *APiKL2*. Coverage of mapped reads were plotted in histograms shaded in grey. HPI = hours post-inoculation.

APiKL2 and APiKL5 are not expressed in field transcriptomics samples of naturally occurring wheat blast infection

We next mapped the raw reads of a field transcriptomics dataset of the 2016 wheat blast outbreak in Bangladesh [9,10] to the wheat blast reference genome assembly of the Bolivian isolate B71 (Peng et al., 2019). Previous genomics analyses have shown that wheat blast isolates collected in Bangladesh are closely related to B71 [14]. We chose sample 12 of infected wheat tissue for this analysis as this sample yielded the highest ratio of fungal to plant reads with 18.6% of the reads mapping to the wheat blast isolate BR32 [10]. We identified the genomic location of effector genes using TBLASN and visualized the RNA-seq read coverage in IGV as described above. In total, we analyzed expression 15 effector genes, including the APiKL family members APiKL2 and APiKL5 as well as several previously characterized effectors, many of which have an avirulence function during infection of *M. oryzae*. Expression of these effectors was variable in the analyzed condition (Fig 2). We detected expression of 11 out of

15 effectors, although expression of Slp1 and AVR1-CO39 was very low. For four effector genes, including AVR-Pita3, PWT3, and the APikL family members APikL2 and APikL5, we did not detect any expression under the observed conditions.

Fig 2. Plot of wheat blast RNA-Seq read coverage in Integrative genomics viewer. Alignment of RNA-Seq data from infected field samples of wheat blast isolates of *M. oryzae* mapped to a selection of known effector genes in B71, including *APikL2* and *APikL5*. Coverage of mapped reads were plotted in histograms shaded in grey. HPI = hours post-inoculation. Gene models corresponding to the effector genes are marked in red.

CONCLUSIONS

In this Technical Note, we analysed expression of several effectors, including the APikL family members AVR-Pik, APikL2, and APikL5 in the rice infecting isolate Ina168 and wheat blast samples collected during the 2016 wheat blast outbreak in Bangladesh. We found that most of

the analysed effectors are expressed under these conditions (Figs 1 and 2). However, several effector genes are not or only weakly expressed under the conditions observed in this study. These include the APiKL family effector candidates APiKL2 and APiKL5, but also some well-characterized effectors such as AVR1-CO39, AVR-Pita3, Slp1, and PWT3 (Fig 2). Whereas the function of APiKL2 and APiKL5 still needs to be determined, the role of the latter during infection and in host specialization is well-documented. AVR1-CO39 is translocated into the host plant cells where it interacts with an integrated HMA domain in the plant immune receptor RGA5 [15]. Presumably, the virulence function of AVR1-CO39 is mediated by interaction with HMA-domain containing plant proteins, similar to AVR-Pik and potentially other APiKL family members [1,4,16]. AVR-Pita3 belongs to a three gene family of metalloprotease like proteins [17]. Whereas an avirulence function has been demonstrated for AVR-Pita1 and 2 in response to the resistance gene Pita, no resistance gene against AVR-Pita3 is known to date. Slp1 is a LysM-domain containing effector that is secreted to the apoplast during infection and suppresses chitin triggered immune responses in the host plant [18]. Lastly, PWT3 has been implicated in defining host-specificity through its cognate resistance gene RWT3 [19]. Despite the lack of RNA-seq read coverage support, these effector genes have a demonstrated role during infection and in determining host-specificity of the blast fungus. Thus, to this end and albeit the lack of expression in the analyzed conditions, we cannot draw any conclusions regarding the function of APiKL family effectors described here and in Bentham et al. [1]. In the future, genetic and transcriptomics data from infections of uncultivated grass hosts, such as *Lolium spp.* or *Stenotaphrum spp.* will help to shed light on the potential function of APiKL family members in the multihost blast fungus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

RNA-Seq data from *M. oryzae* isolate Ina168 during the early stages of infection, (12, 24, 36 and 48 HPI) [7] on peeled epidermal cotyledon tissue of susceptible barley *Hordeum vulgare* cv. ‘Nigrate’, were mapped to the genome sequence of Ina168 using STAR (Dobin et al., 2013) using default parameters. Mapped read alignments were visualized in IGV v2.3.91 [20]. RNA-Seq reads were downloaded from GenBank Sequence Read Archive with accessions DRR195588-DRR195602.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interest.

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